

Appendix L: Interview transcript with a domain expert

1.

Interviewer: Could you briefly describe your role and experience in the field of Industry 5.0? Which aspects of Industry 5.0 do you work with most?

Interviewee: The concept of Industry 5.0 is relatively new and encompasses elements of sustainable development, an emphasis on a human-centred society, responsibility, and other dimensions as well, such as societal resilience. I have been working with these topics for quite some time, even though years ago they were not framed within this conceptualisation of Industry 5.0. After the Japanese concept of Society 5.0 entered public and thus research and academic discourse, the term or concept of Industry 5.0 also emerged. I was able to identify with it very quickly, because for more than a decade I have been dealing with topics related to our relationship with the environment and the planet, and thus with responsible environmental practices, planetary awareness, planetary consciousness, as well as topics connected to improving employment opportunities for vulnerable groups, such as persons with disabilities and migrants. In fact, over the past decade these themes have merged with contemporary trends such as digitalisation, virtual society, and so on. With this hybrid that connects different systems and different environments together. I would say that the concept of Industry 5.0 has, in a way, further focused or guided my previous work in this direction.

2.

Interviewer: How do you view human-centredness as one of the key elements of Industry 5.0?

Interviewee: I view this in a longer historical perspective. When we speak about Industry 5.0, the first word is industry. Industrial society began roughly 200-250 years ago with the aim of easing work processes, or accelerating them, speeding up production, in principle, all these shifts caused a significant burden for workers and employees. The focus was not on employees, but much more on the product itself. At the same time, alongside various other societal changes, from wars to the trade union movement and so on. People gradually began to resist, and the vision of technological development has also been to improve quality of life and, of course, the quality of work as well. Every time something new emerges, the boundary becomes somewhat blurred between whether we are talking about production efficiency or the individual or group operating within a production process.

These are long-established theories. For example, Blumer discussed how, with the Third Industrial Revolution, the quality of the work process for employees improved. The technologies of the Fourth Industrial Revolution introduced something dramatically new in relative perspective. For employees and more generally, as smart production processes, robotisation, and the introduction and development of artificial intelligence began to take hold, we have to ask what the role of the human being is now. Is the human role to innovate? Is it to serve through production processes? Or also to be satisfied and happy while performing work, because it still holds that work, in a way, defines us.

Therefore, what I understand as human-centred society or production is that it takes the human being into account as a kind of centre of the entire process. Everything we do should improve people's quality of life, while also considering the well-being of the entire planet, and not focusing solely on profit or the final product, but also on those who are employed. I would say a multi-layered perspective is important here, and which perspective is relevant depends on the circumstances.

I would also like to add that human-centredness is a concept that has been present for quite some time in public discourse, policy-making discourse, and academic discourse, and in my view it is not sufficient, because we still live in an anthropocentric society. From this, very significant problems arise, problems that we are already confronting and will face even more in the future. Human-centredness, in the sense of discussing ethics, quality of life, and taking into account the wishes and needs of individuals and groups, means that this must be viewed more broadly: we are part of a wider system, namely the planetary system. This has become inseparable for me in recent years, also in my research, scientific, and professional work. The vision of a good life, something already discussed in Ancient Greece, where eudaimonia was a key concept of a society in which people can prosper, is achievable if different actors and stakeholders approach matters in a comprehensive and holistic way. Human-centredness should therefore be understood in that manner as well.

3.

Interviewer: Have you been involved in projects where knowledge was formally modelled?

Interviewee: I am not sure whether I will be able to answer this question as well as you might want. In the way you have framed it, I have not participated in such work. In projects where we addressed the development and understanding of digital tools for improving employment opportunities for vulnerable and disadvantaged groups, we conducted research and, based on findings and conclusions, arrived at important concepts, categorised them, and searched for relationships between them. If that constitutes a taxonomy, then yes.

One of these projects produced a platform as the main output, enabling both employers and those seeking employment or those already employed to access information, become familiar with digital innovations in general and allowing those who need work to participate in a learning process designed for them. At the same time, through their feedback, they contributed to establishing new learning content and learning processes.

More broadly, I am a humanist, a social scientist. In a project I led, funded by ARIS, we examined responsible action among individuals in Slovenia, with the aim of studying how reflexivity or relational reflexivity can contribute to social change. What we refer to as social morphogenesis, i.e., change in society created by actors. We were building on various measurement instruments, such as a survey questionnaire, and for these purposes we needed to understand what certain concepts mean to people and how they are connected.

The key concepts we addressed were reflexivity, responsibility, the environment, society, and of course digitalisation, the technological system, or the technological environment. This extension of an existing taxonomy or of conceptual understanding was mainly about including the technological environment as an independent environment, alongside the social and natural environments, while acknowledging that it interacts with the others. We primarily did this through pilot studies: we engaged in in-depth conversations with various experts, actors, and the targeted population, and then sought to understand what certain concepts represent and what lies behind them. With such background, we can understand the relationships between concepts. If we do not understand the context of a concept, it is difficult to identify deeper relationships, because those that are obvious at first glance are superficial and do not contribute anything new. What remains hidden or less visible is precisely what we investigate. So yes, there have been several such projects.

4.

Interviewer: What experience do you have with large language models? For which tasks do you typically use them?

Interviewee: I see these tools as a type of assistant. For now, this level of AI use is sufficient for me. I still approach so-called agentic AI somewhat cautiously and with a more critical research perspective. I use them thoughtfully for tasks that can save me time, mostly related to my work. My use is relatively basic. We used to joke that Google knows everything. Now, in a way, we no longer search for things on Google unless it makes sense, but ask one of these tools instead. In my work, I most prefer using Perplexity. At least based on the information I received or was instructed on and as my experience has confirmed it is oriented toward the academic environment, meaning it generally supports outputs with verifiable sources, rather than only providing information that may be hallucinated, irrelevant, or fabricated.

5.

Interviewer: As a domain expert, which concepts and entities do you consider key within the domain of Industry 5.0?

Interviewee: As I said, some are general concepts, but when we focus them on a concrete situation, we translate them into a tree structure that then expands. These include human-centredness, resilience, sustainability, responsibility, and above all a holistic perspective and an awareness of the interconnectedness of the planetary system, which also includes the technological system.

If we imagine losing access to natural resources, electricity is a natural resource, even if we produce it with the help of technology, as it still originates from natural resources or if we remove all the components that enable all these devices to function, we have nothing. Not to mention that we breathe air and eat, and so on. For me, the key perspective is this comprehensive interweaving: the interweaving of all environments and systems, human, social, natural, and technological, because if we understand this interconnectedness, responsibility, sensitivity, ethics, and resilience follow automatically.

If I may use a widely known metaphor: if we see something as part of our body, we will not harm it. No one wants to cut off a finger unless it is a pathological act. If we are capable of

seeing other people as part of ourselves, of course, individual autonomy, integrity, and agency remain important; I do not mean to diminish that, but above all recognising interdependence. If we see others as interdependent with ourselves, and place this within the context of the planet, then our practices change naturally.

However, this is not only an individual issue; it must also be translated to other levels. The vision of Industry 5.0 is valuable because it originates from the macro level, i.e., from policy-makers. These are important considerations, beyond merely discussing industrial development itself. It also concerns the role and meaning of that development. This concept or vision is not primarily about technological development alone, not exclusively, but rather about why it matters and how it will affect our lives.

6.

Interviewer: What challenges do you observe in the implementation of Industry 5.0?

Interviewee: Industry 5.0 is still developing, not only in terms of conceptualisation but especially in terms of implementation. People and stakeholders who work on this, including in Slovenia, had an important event just last week. Every year there is at least one such event, or several.

I see an additional challenge in implementation because practices are so deeply entrenched at all levels, from production to thinking patterns and ways of life. Again, I see these as strongly interconnected, and it is difficult to realise something without “stepping on someone’s toes.” For instance, we want to protect the natural environment and river biospheres, but then what about hydroelectric power plants? There is always someone who responds, with their own opinion and their own place in society.

In my view, this will require a great deal of reflection and coordination, which will certainly influence how implementation itself shapes perception and contextualisation. We need to look at a concrete example. As long as we speak in general terms, interconnectedness remains abstract, but with a concrete case such as a company or an initiative we can more precisely identify the important aspects of Industry 4.0 and the vision of 5.0, where limitations and dilemmas occur in implementation, and how to address them. This is a general concept and general vision, but we must learn how to apply it in concrete situations and not forget it.

7.

Interviewer: Where do you see important “bridges” between technology, organisation, the human factor, and sustainability in this domain?

Interviewee: I can share my general view. In more concrete situations we could add more substance. Bridges are already present in the fact that society would not exist without people. In order not only to survive but also to prosper, people developed certain social mechanisms, social structures, and so on. At the same time, all human development and social development are inseparably linked to technological development.

From the very beginning, when we talk about breakthroughs of the human species, Homo sapiens, this is inseparable from technological development in many forms: the use of tools, and later even the development of speech. Symbolic communication is itself a kind of technology, and it enabled technological development. What we today understand as technological development, however, is again largely a matter of the last 200-250 years of modern, industrial society.

These environments have always been interwoven and intertwined, but now they are becoming increasingly complex, extensive, complicated, and interconnected. So the bridges are already present at the very foundation, but in practice we often emphasise only one dimension or a few dimensions within a given environment.

If we look at a company producing a product, following technological trends is certainly meaningful, because what becomes outdated dies off. We can also view things organically, even when talking about technology: competitiveness, existence, and prosperity on the market, this is the perspective of entrepreneurs, directors, those on that side. Employees who are satisfied and creative should not be seen merely as added value, but as something that ought to be the foundation of employment. Yet because the world is already so volatile and unstable, companies may hire low-skilled workers who will work and become alienated from their labour. But in the long run, creativity is missing, and a positive atmosphere is missing, both of which research indicates are important for a company to prosper.

When highly qualified labour is needed, good relationships and creativity must be encouraged in any case, because otherwise it is not worthwhile for anyone. And all of this can be understood

as embedded in broader contexts: a company matters for communities, for the local environment, and so on, leading again to a global perspective. We should be aware that this perspective is in everyone's interest, because only when we are extremely short-term do we fail to see these advantages. Unfortunately, many people do act in this short-term way, both in planning the future and in learning from the past. We can see that within just two generations, people can forget what happened, even horrors.

The bridges would not only be established, but also more visible. However, action is needed at all levels of society. We must begin early, already in primary socialisation at home, but also from the very start of formal education. Such issues should be an inseparable part of all content. That is, we should not only provide information to small children and encourage cognitive and memory abilities but also promote empathy and a sense of interconnectedness because we are far more vulnerable than we think.

8.

Interviewer: In this part, I presented artefacts created with LLM:

- A list of proposed concepts and their taxonomy for Industry 5.0.
- Two examples of relations (one simple, one more complex) that connect classes at different locations within the taxonomy.

A list of concepts and a proposed taxonomy were shown on the screen. How do you assess this set of concepts?

Interviewee: Overall, the set of concepts seems sensible and useful as a starting point. However, I think it is important to emphasise that it is not only the classification of concepts into a hierarchy that matters, but also the definitions themselves. Definitions are often rather topological, they explain a concept using a term that is essentially already implied in the concept itself. From my more social-scientific and humanistic background, I find the set of concepts useful and largely meaningful, but the quality of the definitions is not sufficient everywhere.

9.

Interviewer: In your opinion, are the key concepts included? What important elements are missing?

Interviewee: The most honest answer is that I cannot say with certainty that all key concepts are included, but I can say that many very important concepts are certainly present. When I look, for example, at goals, strategies, training, and similar concepts, I would say these are conceptually strong elements that clearly belong within the framework of Industry 5.0. On the other hand, I think the concepts associated with Industry 5.0 are still evolving. I would not limit myself exclusively to what we currently find in political and strategic documents (human-centred, sustainable, resilient), because the vision will still change in practice.

When concrete implementations occur, real examples often reveal new and more profound concepts. Therefore, I would say that an important portion of the key concepts is included, but there is room for further development, especially based on concrete implementation cases.

10.

Interviewer: Is there anything you consider redundant or incorrectly placed within the scope of Industry 5.0?

Interviewee: Some classes and concepts seem to me less specific to Industry 5.0 and more generally industrial or societal. One example is “product.” A product is certainly part of Industry 5.0, but it is also part of all previous industrial revolutions, the first, second, third, and fourth. A product as such is not something unique to Industry 5.0. Rather, the question is how the product is embedded in the new conceptual framework.

I think similarly about other classes such as various systems, robots, and certain types of information content. All of this is also clearly present in Industry 4.0. The key question is whether the ontology captures them as general industrial concepts or as something conceptually transformed within Industry 5.0.

From a social-science perspective, Industry 5.0 necessarily includes at least three basic systems: the social system, the technological system, and the natural system. I would see these three almost as foundational, very high-level concepts. Everything that is part of society belongs to the social system; everything technological belongs to the technological system; everything that is the natural environment belongs to the natural system. This is something I miss in this taxonomy, or it is less emphasised.

11.

Interviewer: How do you evaluate the proposed taxonomy of classes?

Interviewee: I have reservations about some specific placements. For example, the class “information content entity” for the industrial domain under “generically dependent continuant.” This is formally correct, but it raises the question of whether this implies that documents are not updated, that they are stable or whether it is something very dynamic in practice. Here I would need clearer contextualisation. Overall, I would say the taxonomy is solid as an engineering or ontological product, but it does not necessarily align with how we would conceptually design a system from a social-science or broader perspective.

12.

Interviewer: Do you think the superclasses are sufficiently general and the subclasses meaningfully more specific?

Interviewee: I would say that some superclasses are not sufficiently aligned in terms of content with the vision of Industry 5.0. As I mentioned, I would personally see the social system, the technological system, and the natural system as very high-level superclasses, and only then place concrete industrial processes, products, human actors, information, and so forth within them. In that sense, superclasses such as “material entity,” “process,” and “information content entity” do function, but they are not necessarily the most intuitive if we start from the goals of Industry 5.0.

13.

Interviewer: Where do you see illogical structures or potential improvements?

Interviewee: One example where I have a strong concern is the class “human actor,” which is placed under “material entity.” I do not understand a human actor merely as a material entity. For me, a human being is an open system that is simultaneously biological, psychological, and social. If we represent it ontologically as only a material entity, I think that is not in line with the vision of Industry 5.0, which is intended to be human-friendly and to place the human being at the centre.

More generally, it seems to me that parent-child relations between classes do not reflect the complexity of social and technological systems. I would say it would be meaningful to reorganise the taxonomy in some parts according to how social sciences understand systems and their components.

14.

Interviewer: Here are two examples of relations connecting classes in different parts of the taxonomy (one simple, one more complex). How do you evaluate them? Do the relations adequately reflect real connections in Industry 5.0?

Interviewee: In the first, simpler relation, for example, an industrial process that supports the circular economy, the relation itself does not seem problematic to me. The claim that an industrial process supports the circular economy, and that the circular economy is supported by industrial processes, is entirely reasonable. The distinctions between the process as a whole and the process steps are also logical.

In the second, more complex relation, where “human actor” appears as a subclass of “material entity” and at the same time as a subclass of a human role, I have greater reservations. I previously mentioned that I do not agree with the premise that “human” is a “material entity.” It seems to me that such placement is not in line with the vision of Industry 5.0, which seeks to understand the human being more broadly, not only materially.

Relations linking processes with resources (energy, materials, tools, human resources) are meaningful and appropriate. However, where relations concern the human actor and their roles, I would conceptually place things differently.

15.

Interviewer: Where would you expect additional important relations that are not captured here?

Interviewee: I would expect more relations connecting the vision and implementation, how practical solutions feed back into redefining concepts; relations between social actors, for example different stakeholder groups, their interests and power; relations between humans and the natural system, not only humans and technology; and relations that reflect the complexity of social fields in which Industry 5.0 is enacted.

16.

Interviewer: If you were to summarise your view in one sentence, how would you complete the following statement? The use of large language models for designing and implementing ontologies in the field of Industry 5.0...

Interviewee: ...is important and meaningful, but it requires a certain degree of caution and an emphasis on human creativity and cognitive processes.

17.

Interviewer: Would you like to add anything else that we have not mentioned?

Interviewee: At this point I do not have anything particularly additional, but of course we could discuss this topic for a long time, as it is extremely topical. In my view, it makes sense to look at Industry 5.0 and the use of large language models on two levels: the general level (vision, principles, political documents) and the level of concrete examples. When we talk about the circular economy or industry in general, we remain very abstract. But when we have a concrete example in social science we would call it a “concrete social field” more in-depth concepts begin to emerge on that basis. LLMs are useful, but we must continuously verify and upgrade concepts through concrete practices and human thinking.